

THE ADVANTAGES OF COLLABORATIVE LEARNING

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Annotation: Collaborative learning is an educational approach to teaching and learning that involves groups of learners working together to solve a problem, complete a task, or create a product. This article outlines benefits of learning in collaboration style, begins with the concept of the term and continues with the advantages created by collaborative methods.

Key words: Collaborative learning, benefits, advantages, collaborative methods.

Collaboration is the practice of working together to achieve a common goal.

Collaboration is important because whether students realize it or not, they'll probably work with other people for the rest of their lives. Virtually every job requires someone to work with another person at some point, even if it's for something as simple as what to get for lunch. Practicing collaboration and teamwork helps students understand how to address a problem, pitch solutions, and decide the best course of action. It's also helpful for them to learn that other people don't always have the same ideas that they do. In fact, as students practice collaboration more and more, they'll learn that they have almost none of the same ideas that others do. This can affect students in one of two ways. First, it could discourage them since nobody seems to agree with them that often. Second, it could embolden them because they realize they're bringing something unique to every conversation. As a teacher, it's crucial that you encourage students to look at themselves through that second lens. That way, students learn that they should speak up when they have an idea.

They may not be on the money 100% of the time — and some of their peers may have strong, opinionated reactions — but it'll teach them to speak up when they're working with others. Learning how to work effectively and respectfully with other people is an important life skill. Collaborative activities are also excellent for English language learners because they encourage speaking and listening skills.

Learning tip. Put books, chairs and other objects in places where people might bump into them. Choose one family member to walk through the obstacle course while blindfolded. Ask another family member to guide them through the obstacle course, by saying directions in English (e.g. left, right, stop, take one step back). **Responsibility.** Responsibility is about encouraging children to make a difference to the world in which they live. Children learn that they can inspire and motivate others when they lead by example.

Learning tip. Ask your child to be responsible for teaching another family member some English. For example, this might involve teaching them three new English words a day and testing them at the end of each week. This is a great activity for language learners. Teaching someone else is one of the best ways to learn. There are many theories about how collaborative learning might benefit pupil outcomes. Through collaboration, pupils may develop explanation, demonstration, problem-solving, and metacognitive skills, or pupils may benefit from sharing the load of challenging tasks. It is important that schools ensure that within collaborative learning:

- all pupils, particularly pupils with low prior attainment, are supported to fully participate
- the make-up of pairings and groups is carefully considered
- teachers promote good practice in collaboration – for example modelling high quality discussions so that collaborative activities are productive

- teachers carefully monitor collaborative activities and support pupils that are struggling or not contributing

There is a broad range of approaches to collaborative or cooperative learning involving different kinds of organisation and tasks across the curriculum. Not all of the specific approaches to collaborative learning adopted by schools have been evaluated, so it is important to evaluate any new initiative in this area. Professional development is likely to be required to maximise the effectiveness of approaches and monitor the impact of different approaches in the classroom. Collaborative learning can describe a large variety of approaches, but effective collaborative learning requires much more than just sitting pupils together and asking them to work . There is some evidence that collaboration can be supported with competition between groups, but this is not always necessary, and can lead to learners focusing on the competition rather than the learning it aims to support. Most of the positive approaches include the promotion of talk and interaction between learners.

The evidence indicates that groups of 3–5 is most effective for collaborative learning approaches – there are smaller positive impacts for both paired work and collaborative learning activities with more than 5 pupils in a group. There is also some evidence that collaborative learning approaches are particularly promising when used to teach science.

Used literatures:

1. Kambaraliyeva, I. (2024, April). BREAKING LANGUAGE BARRIERS: HOW LANGUAGE LEARNING PROMOTES GLOBAL UNDERSTANDING. In *Conference Proceedings: Fostering Your Research Spirit* (pp. 615-617).
2. Aripovna, R. S. (2024). THE COGNITIVE WAYS TO LEAD AN ADVANCED LEARNER TO MAKE SELF-ASSESSMENT: Yangi O'zbekiston taraqqiyotida tadqiqotlarni o'rni va rivojlanish omillari. *Yangi*

- O'zbekiston taraqqiyotida tadqiqotlarni o'rni va rivojlanish omillari*, 7(3), 116-121.
3. Bazarova, D. (2022). Variability of phraseological units. *Science and innovation*, 1(B7), 483.
 4. Bazarova, D. (2024). TA'LIM RUS TILIDA OLIV BORILADIGAN GURUHLARDA "O 'ZBEK TILIDA SO 'Z TARKIBI" MAVZUSINI O 'RGATISH TAJRIBASIDAN. *O 'ZBEK TILINING XORIJDA O 'QITILISHI: TA'LIM NAZARIYASI VA AMALIYOTI*, 1(01), 88-90.
 5. Aliqulova, M. (2024). АНАЛИЗ ИЗУЧЕНИЯ ЯЗЫКА И СТИЛЯ ПРОИЗВЕДЕНИЙ АИ КУПРИНА. *O 'ZBEK TILINING XORIJDA O 'QITILISHI: TA'LIM NAZARIYASI VA AMALIYOTI*, 1(01), 82-87.
 6. Алиқулова, М. (2023). ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ЭПИТЕТОВ В ПРОИЗВЕДЕНИЯХ АИ КУПРИНА. *Scientific progress*, 4(5), 387-390.
 7. Khasanova, S., Akisheva, N., & Zholayeva, M. (2023). Methodological aspects of tax planning in the context of sustainable development. *Revista Gestão & Tecnologia*, 23(3), 286-298.
 8. Sarsebaevich, A. M., & Qizi, J. Z. R. (2024). УЗБЕКИСТОН ХУДУДЛАРИДА ҚИШЛОҚ ХУЖАЛИГИ МАҲСУЛОТЛАРИНИ ИШЛАБ ЧИҚАРИШ САМАРОДОРЛИГИ ТАҲЛИЛИ. *Science and innovation*, 3(Special Issue 24), 616-621.
 9. Tajenova, G. E., Baijanov, S. X., Abishov, M. S., & Madreimov, A. K. (2022). PROVIDING AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTS TO THE POPULATION AND FINANCING IT BY THE STATE WAYS TO IMPROVE SUPPORT. *NeuroQuantology*, 20(22), 1598.
 10. Utegenova, S., & Mirzabaeva, U. (2024). TODAY'S IMPORTANCE AND PROSPECTS OF AUDIT ACTIVITIES IN UZBEKISTAN. *Евразийский журнал академических исследований*, 4(6), 93-95.
 11. Utegenova, S., & Rozumova, D. (2024). DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVING TAX AUDIT. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(6).

12. Utegenova, S., & Oralbaeva, F. (2024). O'zbekiston iqtisodiyotiga xorijiy investitsiyalar oqimini oshirishda mamlakatning investitsion muhiti jozibadorligini oshirish. *Журнал академических исследований нового Узбекистана*, 1(6), 131-134.
13. Сарсеновна, Ш. Д. (2023). ВЫБОР УПРАВЛЕНЧЕСКИХ РЕШЕНИЙ ПО МОМЕНТУ ДОСТИЖЕНИЯ МАКСИМАЛЬНОЙ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ПРОИЗВОДСТВА ХЛОПКА-СЫРЦА.
14. Шамшетова, Д. С. (2023). ЗАТРАТЫ КАК КРИТЕРИИ К ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЮ УРОВНЯ УРОЖАЙНОСТИ И ЦЕНООБРАЗОВАНИЯ ДЛЯ РЕАЛИЗАЦИИ ХЛОПКА-СЫРЦА ПРОИЗВЕДЕННОГО В УСЛОВИЯХ ПРИАРАЛЬЯ. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 34, 319-324.
15. Tulenova, K., Ubaydullayeva, S., Gaziyeva, R., Mamayusupov, U., Mamadjonova, M., & Turdikulova, E. (2024, June). The Introduction of Information Technologies Into Educational and Laboratory Complexes is an Important Step Towards the Digitalization of Uzbekistan. In *2024 4th International Conference on Technology Enhanced Learning in Higher Education (TELE)* (pp. 48-53). IEEE.
16. Qurbonazarovna, M. M. (2024). OZBEKISTON TARAQQIYOTINING YANGI DAVRIDA TALIM SIFATINI OSHIRISHNING SINERGETIK IMKONIYATLARI. *Science and innovation*, 3(Special Issue 18), 65-67.
17. Turabekova, S., & Ibadova, N. (2024, April). Different Ways Of Improving Listening Skill In Learning Foreign Languages. In *Conference Proceedings: Fostering Your Research Spirit* (pp. 236-238).
18. Ibadova, N. (2024, April). Nutqdagi Ekspressivlikning Leksik Tasnifi. In *Conference Proceedings: Fostering Your Research Spirit* (pp. 319-323).
19. Axmatilloevna, I. N. (2024). Specific Characteristics Of Text Category. *Open Access Repository*, 10(3), 131-136.

20. Qurbanazarovna, M. M. (2023). PRELIMINARY IDEAS OF NECESSITY AND ACCIDENT. *World Bulletin of Social Sciences*, 26, 44-46.

